

FASHION

A constantly evolving cultural and social phenomenon;
 Reflects identity, values, and historical contexts;
 For Simmel, it is a continuous cycle of imitation and innovation;
 For Foucault and Barthes, fashion is an artistic expression and system of meanings;

FASHION

SHOW

A hybrid space between art and performance;
 Platform for visual and emotional narratives;
 The fashion show reflects cultural values and contexts;
 By incorporating performative elements, its expressive dimension is expanded, bringing it closer to an artistic and three-dimensional language;

A PERFORMANCE

Ephemeral, Experiential, and Participatory;
 Influences of avant-garde movements (Dadaism, Surrealism);
 Integrating with fashion to create visual and emotional narratives;
 Lara Torres, Storytailors, Constança Entrudo;

NEW MEDIA

Digital revolution redefines fashion production, consumption, and promotion;
 Digital fashion and the Metaverse emerge as new creative territories ;

New Media (Manovich)

It notes that the impact of digital technologies is causing an even broader and deeper transformation in the way culture is produced, distributed, and communicated;

Fuery, 2017

New Media = cultural rupture, not just technical;
 A space for new ideas, emerging practices, and cultural redefinition;

Digital Fashion and Metaverse (Kawamura, 2023)

Fashion in the Metaverse as a new creative space;
 Globalization of fashion on digital platforms;
 Experimenting with new production and distribution techniques;

